

The Use of GeoAI Techniques for Gathering, Storing, and Analyzing Historical Agroecological Data

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Abstract

Most historical sources, available in multiple formats (e.g., tabular and analog data), contain valuable geographic information. This data can be transformed to generate both quantitative and qualitative insights, enabling the creation of digital maps and unlocking significant potential for scientific analysis. However, the use of historical data presents several challenges: 1. Sources need to be digitized; 2. Collections are often spread across multiple archives; 3. Metadata is often unavailable; 4. Standardizing diverse sources and quantitatively reconstructing data from various periods is difficult; 5. The reliability of historical data can be uncertain; 6. There is limited spatial resolution; and 7. Inaccuracies and text legibility issues are common. These challenges underscore the need for novel methodologies aimed at enhancing the quality and quantity of such sources. This paper presents the findings of the exploratory project AgroecoDecipher (2022.09372.PTDC) dedicated to extracting a comprehensive database from historical textual records and analogue map files to trace agroecological patterns. Employing an exploratory methodology grounded in artificial intelligence (AI) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS), the projected solutions include the establishment of routines based on AI tools that combines GIS, machine learning (ML), and Large Language Models (LLMs). Approximately 271 survey books from the 1950s were digitized at the municipal level, with a total sheet count exceeding 42,000. Additionally, more than 100 analogue maps were digitized, processed, and vectorized, resulting in a detailed geodatabase map archive. The results are promising and demonstrate that the integration of AI and geospatial tools has proven essential in transforming raw historical data.

1.0 Introduction

Most historical sources, available in multiple formats (e.g., tabular and analog data), contain valuable geographic information (Knowles, 2005). This data can be transformed to generate both quantitative and qualitative insights, enabling the creation of digital maps and unlocking significant potential for scientific analysis (Gregory and Geddes, 2014; Gregory and Ell, 2007; Knowles, 2008). However, the use of historical data presents several challenges: 1. Sources need to be digitized; 2. Collections are often spread across multiple archives; 3. Metadata is often unavailable; 4. Standardizing diverse sources and quantitatively reconstructing data from various periods is difficult; 5. The reliability of historical data can be uncertain; 6. There is limited spatial resolution; and 7. Inaccuracies and text legibility issues are common. These challenges underscore the need for novel methodologies aimed at enhancing the quality and quantity of available historical data (Murrieta-Flores et al, 2017; Boivin and Crowther, 2021, Viana, 2023). Recognizing the pivotal role of historical sources, this paper presents the findings of the exploratory project AgroecoDecipher (2022.09372.PTDC) dedicated to extracting a comprehensive database from historical textual records and analogue map files to trace agroecological patterns. Detailed data on agroecological conditions are crucial for harmonizing agriculture with natural processes and correlating the impacts of historical human activities with past environmental changes. Moreover, extracting this detailed information contributes significantly to reconstructing historical agroecological conditions and trends, enabling an understanding of potential complex behaviors and dynamics between different variables that describe agricultural systems in Portugal. By employing an exploratory methodology grounded in artificial intelligence (AI) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS), the projected solutions include the establishment of

routines based on machine learning (ML), Large Language Models (LLMs), and OCR. This approach enhances their accessibility for geospatial analysis, enabling the reconstruction and reinterpretation of regional agroecological conditions and trends in Portugal throughout the 20th century. The research presented in this paper pursues four primary objectives: a) digitally transcribe historical text records; b) convert written characters into machine-readable form; c) scan, georeference, and vectorize analog maps; and d) employ K-means cluster-based analysis to group and categorize the textual data from each municipality survey into clusters with similar characteristics. In summary, the overarching results have made substantial contributions to the development of open science and collaborative solutions, including the establishment of routines based on open-source geospatial AI tools. These tools enabled the efficient and accurate conversion of historical records into structured data, significantly enhancing their usability and accessibility for further analysis. The project's outcomes are not only beneficial for contemporary agricultural planning but also contribute to the broader field of geography, history, agronomy, economy, providing a model for future research endeavors.

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Data

The primary historical source for the project is the “Inquérito Agrícola e Florestal do Plano de Fomento Agrário” [Agricultural and Forestry Surveys of the Agricultural Promotion Plan] (Figure 1). These survey books offer detailed local information on edaphoclimatic, agroecological, and physiographic features, such as climate, soil, water, land use, and road networks for all Portuguese municipalities. They contain comprehensive data from the

1950s on nearly every aspect of Portugal's rural economy, including detailed descriptions of agricultural and forestry land uses and their suitability. This source serves as an excellent cartographic reference with high accuracy. For analysis purpose, only 10 surveys were considered (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Copy of the Agricultural and forestry Survey – agrarian development plan for the municipality of Viseu (1953).

Figure 2. Geographic distribution of surveyed municipalities ($n=10$).

2.1.1 Digitization: For the digitization process, Adobe Scan software was used. This specific technological approach ensured the efficiency of our digitization endeavor. After digitization, we applied a two-color system filter—comprising black and white—using an effective binarization technique on the colors of each survey sheet (Figure 3). This step transformed the survey sheets into a binary format, where pixels were represented exclusively in black or white. This process streamlined the data for further analysis, offering enhanced clarity and facilitating the extraction of meaningful insights.

I - CARACTERÍSTICAS GERAIS

A - situação

O concelho de Viseu ocupa aproximadamente a parte central do distrito e até da bem característico e conhecida região de Beira Alta. Ao Norte é limitado pelos concelhos de Castro Verde e Vila Nova de Paiva, ao Sul pelos de Tondela e Melas, e a Oeste já mais a Sudeste; contacta a Nascente com os de Penha, Penalva do Castelo e Mangualde, e a Pente com os de Castelo do Sul e Vouzela. A sua área total é de 50,472 ha de qual 9,388,41 ha (1) é baldia hoje na sua maior parte a ser arborizada pelos Serviços Florestais. Está administrativamente dividido em 30 freguesias as quais, excepto as duas (Occidental e Oriental) que formam a cidade de Viseu, são predominantemente ou exclusivamente rurais.

Cada freguesia tem sempre uma ou mais povoações anexas, tudo indicando portanto uma grande densidade populacional. É de facto, segundo o censo de 1940 é de todos os concelhos do distrito aquele onde a densidade é mais elevada, tanto relativamente à superfície total, como à que apenas constitui propriedade privada.

(1) - Extraída do Reconhecimento dos Baldios de J.C.A.I..

Figure 3. Illustration of a digitally transcribed sheet through the utilization of Adobe Scan software and a two-color system filter—employing a black and white scheme.

2.1.2 Optical Character Recognition (OCR): To convert written characters into machine-readable form, we first identified the optimal OCR software. We used the AI tool ChatGPT version 3.5 to determine the most effective OCR software for our process. ChatGPT identified the top five contenders as Google's Tesseract, Adobe Reader, Abby FineReader, OneNote, and Amazon Textract. We then conducted a comparative assessment by testing all five software options on a single sheet to determine which produced the most accurate text recognition results. Accuracy was evaluated by comparing the number of characters present on the sheet with the OCR recognition results, thereby determining each software's capability to accurately recognize each character. However, despite the generally high accuracy achieved with Amazon Textract, errors from the OCR software still occurred, which could potentially affect the results. To ensure the integrity of the processed survey data, the OCR output was further corrected using generative artificial intelligence. This process was conducted with the assistance of ChatGPT version 3.5.

2.1.3 Scanning, georeferencing and vectorizing analog maps: For the third objective, we focused on scanning, georeferencing, and both automatic and semi-automatic vectorizing of analog maps to create a comprehensive geodatabase map archive. This process involved converting the analog maps into a digital format, georeferencing them to align with spatial data standards, and vectorizing the map features for integration into a geospatial database in QGIS.

2.1.4 Cluster-based analysis: Finally, the third step involves employing K-means cluster-based analysis to group and categorize the textual data from each municipality survey into clusters

with similar characteristics, thereby fostering a more nuanced understanding of patterns and relationships within each municipality. This technique was executed in a Python environment using the 'scikit-learn' library. To initiate the clustering process, we began by removing all stopwords, a list of common words such as determiners or other frequently used words with lesser weight. This removal is pivotal, considering that a higher number of words would adversely impact clustering performance. The list of stopwords was sourced from 'NLTK,' a Python Natural Language Processing library. Following stopwords removal, we computed Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TFIDF). TFIDF is a widely employed metric for determining the weight of each term in a document, calculated based on the term's frequency in that document (Yao & Cong, 2012; Abualigah & Khader, 2017). The optimal number of clusters for k-means was determined using the elbow method. This involved creating a graph with outputs within the specified range of different 'k' values or centroids.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Digitalization and OCR

During the project duration, we successfully digitized 271 survey books from the 1950s at the municipality level, with a total sheet count surpassing 42000. However, for this paper only 10 surveys were considered. Moving on to the second stage of our study, we evaluated five OCR software options. Table 1 provides an accuracy assessment for the digitized sheets. The findings indicated that the software with the highest accuracy was Amazon Textract, achieving an accuracy rate of 72.3% across all surveys. The OCR text was subsequently refined using ChatGPT, resulting in an overall accuracy ranging from approximately 87% to 100%. Table 2 provides an example of the results from two surveys/municipalities.

Software	Accuracy
Google's Tesseract	50%
Adobe Reader	12.4%
Abby FineReader	51.5%
OneNote	16.3%
Amazon Textract	72.3%

Table 1. OCR software accuracy assessment

Case	Nº Characters	OCR precision	ChatGPT precision	Precision increment
1	135	28.89%	98.52%	69.63%
2	206	94.17%	100.00%	5.83%

Table 2. Amazon Textract OCR and ChatGPT accuracy assessment

3.2 Analog maps

Additionally, we digitized, processed and vectorized more than 100 analogue maps, creating a detailed geodatabase map archive (Figure 4). In the context of this study, not all the municipalities analyzed had agricultural maps in their surveys; thus, Figure 4 illustrates the aggregation of the available maps. Although all the maps discussed in this dissertation are identified in Chapter 1 of the survey as "Agricultural zones", there were no guidelines that allowed for the standardization of the nomenclature between the maps. This situation complicated the cartographic representation, as the same class could often be labeled in different ways across

maps, making it difficult to differentiate the classes when aggregating them for the final map. Figure 4 allows for the understanding of the geographical and administrative diversity specific to Portugal, categorized by various classes, suggesting a segmentation of areas based on territorial characteristics, associated with agronomic, environmental, or territorial management purposes (e.g., land use, terrain features, or even property patterns) that influence the territorial structure. Some classes identify specific subzones and categories, such as "High Sub-Zone," "Low Sub-Zone," "Forest Zone," "Arid Zone," among others, indicating that each area was mapped based on precise criteria, such as altitude, soil characteristics, or climatic conditions. Other classes, such as "Ordered Zone" and "Disordered Zone," may indicate regions with higher or lower regulation in land use or urban development. Similarly, classes like "Large Property Zone," "Erosion Zone," and "Protection Zone" indicate elements related to territorial management, whether in terms of environmental protection or land use. Explicit references to "Agricultural Regions" are also highlighted, which may represent the main cultivation areas or economically important zones for agriculture.

Figure 4. Vectorized analog maps

3.3 Cluster-based analysis

Figure 5 displays the elbow graph generated from K-means clustering. The optimal value for 'k' was determined as 4, corresponding to the point of intersection on the graph line (Cui, 2020). Consequently, the results indicated the presence of four clusters with similar characteristics. Figure 6 unveils distinct spatial patterns, showcasing the presence of four clusters and providing valuable insights into the spatial organization and relationships within each municipality survey. When analysing the most frequently used terms in each cluster, the exploratory results reveal distinctive agricultural themes. In Cluster 1, the predominant term was “wine”, while in Cluster 2 it was “rye”. Cluster 3 prominently featured the term “Wine”, and Cluster 4 showcased “maize” and “rye”. In summary, the two-phase approach employed in this study enhances the usability of the survey data, rendering it conducive to advanced analytical techniques for deriving meaningful insights and patterns.

Figure 5. Elbow graph

Figure 6. Clusters-based analysis spatial patterns

4.0 Conclusions

Overall, this research highlights the importance of integrating advanced technologies, such as GIS, ML, and LLMs, to enhance the accessibility and usability of historical data. The methodologies developed and the data digitized through this project offer significant potential for further scientific analysis and contribute to the broader field of historical geography and agroecological research. The overarching results have made substantial contributions to the development of open science and collaborative solutions, including the establishment of routines based on open-source geospatial AI tools for digitization and OCR. These tools enable the efficient and accurate conversion of historical records into structured data, significantly enhancing their usability and accessibility for further analysis. The project's outcomes are not only beneficial for contemporary agricultural planning but also contribute to the broader field of geography, history, agronomy, economy, providing a model for future research endeavours. The extensive collected digital archive provides a valuable resource for geospatial analyse historical agroecological conditions and their impacts on contemporary and future land use planning. Our approach not only preserve valuable historical information but also fosters the development of collaborative solutions for researchers and future interdisciplinary studies. The results are promising and show that the integration of artificial intelligence and geospatial tools has proven essential in transforming raw historical data.

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